

Prepare Early Childhood Teachers for Multicultural Classrooms: Reflection on Practice

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 26,2025</p> <p>Accepted: May 27,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Preservice teacher, Early Childhood Education, Multicultural practice, Program change</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15528438</p>	<p><i>The purpose of this study was to describe preservice early childhood teacher's response to a series of multicultural education activities across the teacher preparation program. After syllabi review for Culturally Responsive Teaching (CRT) content, multicultural education activities were added to course syllabi and implemented in the teacher preparation program. The researcher conducted an in-class CRT workshop with a cohort of early childhood preservice teachers. This cohort was also observed and interviewed during their internship after completing the modified courses. The interview revealed five practical findings: students gained an awareness of multicultural teaching; they built positive relationships with diverse students and their families; they responded to children with comfort, respect, and positivity; they advocated to have children's cultural backgrounds represented in the classroom; and they encouraged children to share about their cultural in small groups. The results were used to evaluate the effectiveness of the programmatic changes that were made to improve students' understanding and implementation of CRT practices.</i></p>

Introduction

Early childhood teachers' racial biases contribute to racial disparities in students' access to educational opportunities, classroom experience, and even expulsion rates. Gilliam and colleagues (2016) examined preschool teachers' implicit biases on preschool expulsions. Preschool teachers in this study watched a video to detect challenging behaviors in children. During the video, teachers' eye gazes were tracked. The group of children in the video was equally balanced in terms of race and gender. Gilliam and colleagues found that teachers gazed longer at Black boys to detect challenging behaviors. Another study by Okonofua and Eberhardt (2015) shows that K-12 teachers react more negatively when reading Black student's disciplinary records, compared to White student's disciplinary records that contain the same level of school violations. Teachers were more likely to recommend suspension for Black students after a second infraction, compared to White students. The relationship between race and challenging behavior leads to racial micro aggressions by early childhood teachers. Evidence also shows that teachers who have the same race as the students exhibit less implicit biases (Gilliam et al., 2016; Rasheed et al., 2020; Wright et al., 2017).

Over the last 20 years, multicultural education in early childhood teacher education programs has improved dramatically.

However, one national study of two- and four- year institutions of higher education found that most teacher education programs offer little or no coursework in cultural diversity (Early & Winton, 2001). The lack of multicultural coursework in teacher education programs resulted in many preservice teachers entering the teaching profession holding various misconceptions, false beliefs, stereotypes, and erroneous attitudes about minorities (Vaughan, 2005). The urgent need for multicultural teacher education is due to changing student demographics and the opportunity gap among students of different demographic groups (Cochran-Smith, 2003; Gay & Howard, 2000; Hodgkinson, 2002). Preservice teachers are facing an increasingly diverse classroom environment. Between 2000 and 2015, the percentage of students enrolled in public schools who were White decreased from 61% to 49%. By 2015, more than 50% of students in public schools were students of color. (McFarland et al., 2018). In contrast, less than 20% of public-school teachers were teachers of color during the same time period (McFarland et al., 2018).

Teacher preparation programs are also challenged by growing globalization, which requires preparing teachers with the knowledge, skills, and understanding of cultural responsiveness and sensitivity in order to teach effectively in schools (Zhao, 2010). Teachers need to have knowledge of what their students bring to school and they need to be sensitive to cultural differences (Zhao, 2010). Recent studies found that when working with young children from diverse socio-cultural backgrounds, it can be challenging to identify their developmental needs, conduct assessments fairly, and collaborate with their families (Banerjee & Luckner, 2014). Most states

do not require teacher education programs to include courses on multicultural teaching practices. Therefore, the need for multicultural teacher preparation is critical (Banerjee & Luckner, 2014).

Theoretical Framework

The discussion of teaching with equity involves multicultural education (Alismail, 2016; Banks & Banks, 2016; Gorski & Dalton, 2020; Sleeter, 2019), social justice and critical thinking (Aronson & Laughter, 2016; Jett, 2013), culturally responsive teaching (Gay & Howard, 2000), and culturally relevant pedagogy (Ladson-Billings, 2003). In this line of research, Banks and Banks (2004) define five dimensions of multicultural education: content integration; the knowledge construction process; prejudice reduction; an equity pedagogy; and an empowering school culture and social structure (Banks & Banks, 2004). Specifically, content integration is using examples and content from various cultures and groups to unpack multicultural education in certain subjects. The knowledge construction process refers to the way students investigate how culture within a discipline influences knowledge construction. Prejudice reduction refers to lessons and activities that help students establish positive attitudes of different cultures. An equity pedagogy requires teachers to analyze how their own understanding of multicultural education influences their teaching. An empowering school culture and social structure is described as a school environment and community that uses multicultural education to empower students. These five dimensions provide a framework for pre-service teachers to engage in racial identity work that will lead to a deeper understanding of other cultures and how to implement culturally responsive practices and equitable school policies.

Meanwhile, many institutions have included multicultural education content in their teacher education programs (Cherng & Davis, 2019; Gay & Howard, 2000; McAllister & Irvine, 2000). Ladson-Billings (2009) offers a pedagogy to help teachers connect with students from diverse cultural backgrounds. This pedagogy is referred to Culturally Responsive Teaching (CRT). Ladson-Billings stated seven principles of CRT: communication of high expectation; active learning and teaching methods; student strengths are identified and nurtured; inclusion of culturally and linguistically teaching; cultural sensitivity; supportive learning environment for diverse cultures; and small group instruction (2009). In the same vein, Bennett and colleagues (2018) built a CRT framework with five foundational components: developing a culturally responsive classroom community; family engagement; critical literacy within a social justice framework; multicultural literature; and culturally responsive print rich environment. Gunn and colleagues further develop the CRT framework by adding five additional pieces: emotion and care, reading aloud, vocabulary, technology, and classroom management.

These various applications and extensions of the CRT framework, help teachers understand, connect, and reflect on students' diversity in the classroom as they implement their teaching practices. Recent studies found that teachers working with young children from diverse socio-cultural backgrounds, struggle with identifying children's developmental needs, conducting assessments fairly, and collaborating with their families (Banerjee & Luckner, 2014; Zhang & Bennett, 2003). Therefore, detailed examples for implementing CRT are needed.

This current study will provide an example of how to teach CRT in a teacher education program. This is important since many teacher education programs do not include courses on CRT practices (Ballantyne et al., 2008; Echevarria et al., 2010; Lutton & Ahmed, 2009).

The standards movement arose with the 1983 publication of *A Nation at Risk: The Imperative for Educational Reform* (Chandler et al., 2012; *A nation at risk: The imperative for educational reform.*, 1983). Subsequently, teachers are held accountable for their students' achievement levels regardless of their background and home circumstances. The standards are in place to ensure students are performing at grade level in the United States (Chandler et al., 2012). In early childhood education, the national standards were developed by the National Association for the Education of Young Children (NAEYC) (Lutton & Ahmed, 2009). The NAEYC standards include cultural competence guidelines for teacher preparation programs that are embedded in each standard to show the connection and importance of these skills in all areas of the curriculum and instruction (Hyson, 2003). With the increase of cultural diversity in the classroom, the NAEYC has provided cultural competence guidelines for using culturally sensitive assessments to determine each child's ability and interests. These standards require preservice teachers to have the knowledge of: 1. How culture influences children's development; 2. How to engage with diverse families; 3. How to develop culturally-appropriate learning experiences (Where we stand on professional preparation standards., 2009). However, research shows that pre-service teachers need to improve their understanding and culture competence skills (Barbarin & Crawford, 2006).

In the recent years, scholars and teacher educators have increased their focus on multicultural teacher education across the nation. CRT as an important component of multicultural education needs to be emphasized in early childhood teacher education programs (Banerjee & Luckner, 2014). Byrne (2013) found that preservice teachers have concerns about multicultural education that are related to relationships, reflection, opportunity, optimism, transparency, and social justice. These concerns were revealed during interviews about challenges teachers face in diverse early childhood classrooms.

In this article, we analyze the courses of an early childhood teacher education program to identify the level of multicultural education content in this program. Then, our discussion focuses on multicultural practices from 27 preservice teachers' experience, which include their course work and internship. In this article, we provide a deep look into multicultural theory and practice when preparing teachers for early childhood classroom.

Method

In this study, the researcher conducted a review of multicultural education activities across a teacher preparation program in a four-year institution. The researcher conducted syllabi review for multicultural education content data, in-class CRT workshop assignments, internship observations and interviews were analyzed. Multicultural practices were added into course syllabi and implemented in the teacher preparation program. The researchers conducted an in-class CRT workshop with a cohort of early childhood preservice teachers. This cohort was also observed and interviewed during their internship after attending modified courses.

Participants

Participants were 27 preservice teachers taking Educational Psychology of Early Childhood course at a four-year university, located in the Midwestern United States. Participants represented a range of cultural, ethnic, and racial diversity. There were Asian, African American, and Latino participants.

All participants were enrolled in the Early Childhood Seminar that is co-taught with the Early Childhood Internship, required courses in this teacher preparation program. In this seminar and internship course, students developed understandings of how children learn from ages birth through nine years, using formal and informal assessment information, child development theory and knowledge of children's cultural and family background to develop individualized learning goals for diverse learners. They were also required to spend 15 hours per week in an early childhood classroom. In addition, this course addresses six NAEYC professional standards for early childhood education: promoting child development and learning; building family and community relationships; observing, documenting, and assessing to support young children and families; using developmentally effective approaches; using content knowledge to build meaningful curriculum; becoming a professional. After completing seminar and internship courses, students are expected to gain the ability to create supportive environments for playful, engaging learning; learn to connect with families as related to care and education of each child; systematically observe and document children's strengths and needs; use child observation and other data to plan; use developmentally effective approaches for guiding children's behaviors; teach through social interactions and other intentional teaching strategies; build and utilize meaningful curriculum to increase child growth in varied developmental/academic areas; and recognize their professional role in early childhood community.

Procedures

CRT workshop: Multicultural Education Activity

The multicultural education activity was presented as a small group project in the Educational Psychology of Early Childhood course. There were 7 small groups in the Educational Psychology of Early Childhood course. Each group designed a lesson plan based on a preschooler's profile. Names and other identity information were removed from the preschooler's profile. Then students developed an individualized lesson plan for the preschooler. After collecting lesson plans from groups, the researcher gave students an introduction to diversity and inclusion in a CRT workshop. The CRT workshop started with a brainstorm activity of the social aspects of diverse population in public schools. All groups presented their results after the brainstorming: family, ethnic, social-economic, parent background, disability, minority, foster care, English as second language, etc.

The lesson plans were given back to each group to modify with a focus on a certain diversity component. They modified their lesson plans response to the question: "How will you change your lesson plan address the diversity components in the preschooler's profile? For example, one of the modified lesson plans was adding labeled food names on the food toys for students with English as second language (Table 1).

Data Collection

Syllabi review

As a starting point of this study, researchers applied content analysis approach to investigate culturally appropriate practices in nine cultural competence components with five early childhood education course syllabi (Author, 2018). The nine cultural competence components include: awareness of socio-cultural competence teaching; visualized presence of family diversity; communication of family values, culture, identity and language; understanding family's culturally-based goals for their children; evaluate teacher-parent relationship; reflection on teacher's beliefs and practices; using formal and informal strategies. The five course syllabi examined are: course A. Learning and Assessment in Early Childhood Inclusive Classrooms; course B. Young Children, Their Families, and Their Society; course C. Early Childhood Classroom Organization & Management; course D. Early Childhood Internship Evaluation; course E. Administration of Child Development

Centers. This investigation focused on identifying courses assignments, readings, and activities, based on the NAEYC standards and guidelines for cultural competence.

This content analysis section identified course assignments, readings and activities that focus on culturally appropriate practices in a four-year university. Based on the NAEYC standards and guidelines for cultural competence we developed a checklist. The checklist contains a list of culturally appropriate practices and a rating scale with 3 categories – minimum amount of content (0-2 items), acceptable amount of content (3-4 items), and exceptional amount of content (5-6 items). The checklist categories are: 1. Evidence of awareness of socio-cultural competent teaching, like teaching materials and interactions reflect value for children’s home languages and culture; 2. Evidence that all children and families’ images in the program are presented on the walls and by a family presence in program activities; 3. Ensure communication with families about their children’s assessment findings is in a culturally sensitive way, respecting family values, culture, identity and home language; 4. Invite families to share their culturally- based goals for their children’s progress and input from families in setting learning goals for children; 5. Use parent questionnaires in appropriate languages on how satisfied they were with teacher-parent communication; 6. Aware of cultural influences on their own beliefs and practices. Use self-report questionnaires to ask teachers to identify effective practices, areas of weakness and strength in teaching with children and families from diverse back grounds; 7. Use a variety of formal and informal strategies, like conversations and questionnaires, to learn about socioeconomic, linguistic, racial, religious and cultural difference of families from diverse back grounds; 8. Create a welcoming learning environment including representation of traditions, history and holidays of program participants in the classroom and in daily activities; 9. Provide opportunities for children and their families to share their culture by storytelling, using puppets, other oral tradition, video, films, music, etc(2010 NAEYC standards for initial & advanced early childhood professional preparation programs: Initial standards summary, 2010).

Field Observation

This part of the study provides new evidence and understanding about how preservice teachers in internship respond to multicultural education in early childhood classrooms after increasing multicultural education content and activities in the early childhood program by including a CRT workshop. After the CRT workshop, I observed students’ use of culturally responsive teaching practices in their early childhood education internship. We conducted observations and interviews to gather data on their use of culturally responsive teaching practices.

Debrief

Before the field experience observation started, the researcher compiled various elements to be recorded (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015). The elements include positive climate; negative climate; teacher sensitivity; regard for student perspective based on student interest and point of view; behavior management; productivity; instructional learning formats; concept development; quality of feedback; and language modeling. This involves observing the surroundings of the setting and providing a written description of the context. The researcher also took extra time to record the settings of each observation by writing keywords and drawing outlines of the classroom. The researcher looked at the frequency and duration of those activities/interactions and other subtle factors, such as informal, unplanned activities, symbolic meanings, nonverbal communication, physical clues, and what should happen that has not happened.

After each observation, the researcher debriefed with the preservice teachers and conducted a semi-structured interview about their use of culturally responsive teaching practices. The interview questions below were based on the topic and the interests of each participants.

1. Have you taught in an early childhood classroom before this internship?
2. How do you feel about teaching in a diverse classroom?
3. Do you consider your internship classroom diverse?
4. Do you think multicultural content is needed in your internship classroom?
5. Do you think the teacher education program prepared you to teach in a diverse classroom? Why and why not?
6. Will you continue to teach in early childhood classroom after graduation? Why and why not?
7. What grade do you prefer to teacher?

Data Analysis

Data Analysis Plan

The researchers followed these steps to analyze the observation data and interview data. For the observation and interview data, the researchers read all the recorded and collected data through first. Then we identified topics for meaningful ideas from the data. Topics were grouped into themes. Open coding was applied to the first step of the data analysis (Marshall & Rossman, 2016). This coding method aims to identify concepts and categories from the transcripts. The researchers were cautious about the patterns in participants’ perceptions. While doing

interviews, the researcher was taking notes with key words. This allowed the researcher to better recall details of the interview.

The interview and observation data were analyzed with three rounds of coding with two raters for reliability. Both raters reviewed each interview transcript multiple times. The first round of coding allowed the researcher to get a big picture of the entire interview and observation. At the second round of coding, the raters coded words like, terms, statements, and other noteworthy phrases. Descriptive sentences were moved into themes and subthemes. Pattern codes identify emergent themes, which are explained by multiple pieces of data (Miles et al., 2014; Saldaña, 2016). This process was repeated until the raters found the themes that best represent the perspectives of participants. The following themes were emerged from content analysis, CRT workshop, internship observation and interview data:

1. Awareness of multicultural teaching
2. Build positive relationships with diverse students and their families.
3. Response students with comfort, respect, and positivity.
4. Allow flexibilities and cultural preference in classrooms.
5. Encourage students to speak and express themselves in small groups.

During the internship, the students were able to apply two of the five dimensions of Banks and Banks (2004) multicultural education model– prejudice reduction and equity pedagogy and Ladson-Billings (2009) CRT model.

Trustworthiness

Building trustworthiness starts with transparency, which means describing and documenting qualitative study. It allows others to scrutinize the research and the evidence used to support findings and conclusions (Yin, 2014). To establish transferability, all the decision making in this study will be documented, as well as the data collection process. All steps of this study will be closely scrutinized by the committee chair. Using the member-checking process, this study established credibility. the researcher will take data and interpretations back to the participants if the intentions were unclear (Creswell & Poth, 2018). To establish dependability, the researcher will conduct audit trails in coding process. The process and product in this study will be examined by a peer researcher who has done studies with similar methodology. Before and after data collection, the researcher will have two debriefing conversations with the committee chair regarding the research design, data collection, and upcoming data analysis. After all, the researcher will keep in mind the potential bias from my own background, culture, previous studies, and personal experience.

Results and Discussion

Syllabi Review Results

Results of the syllabi review indicate that students were well prepared in course B and course C on cultural competence component 1. This means students can provide evidence of awareness of socio-cultural competent teaching, like teaching materials and interactions reflect value for children's home languages and culture. However, data show that other six multicultural components need to be strengthened in the courses.

There are gaps need to be addressed in these five courses:

1. ensure all children and families in the program are visible on the walls and provide a family presence in program activities;
2. ensure the communication with families about their children's assessment findings in a culturally sensitive way, respecting family values, culture, identity, and home language;
3. invite families to share their culturally- based goals for their children's progress and request input from families in setting learning goals for children;
4. use parent questionnaires in appropriate languages on how satisfied they were with teacher-parent communication;
5. be aware of their culture influence on their own beliefs and practices knew how to use self-assessments to identify effective practices, areas of weakness and strength in teaching children and families from diverse background; use a variety of formal and informal strategies, like conversations and questionnaires, to learn about socioeconomic, linguistic, racial, religious, and cultural difference of families from diverse back grounds; create welcoming learning environment including representation of traditions, history, and holidays of program participants in the classroom and in daily activities;
6. provide opportunities for children and their families to share their culture through storytelling, puppets, other oral tradition, video, films, music, etc.

Table 1. Content Analysis Outcome

	Course	A	B	C	D	E
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1. Evidence of awareness of socio-cultural competent teaching, like teaching materials and interactions reflect value for children's home languages and culture	Minimum	Exceptional	Good	Minimum	Minimum
2. Evidence that all children and families in the program are visible on the walls and by a family presence in program activities.	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum
3. Ensure the communication with families about their children's assessment findings is in a culturally sensitive way, respecting family values, culture, identity and home language	Good	Good	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum
4. Invite families to share their culturally- based goals for their children's progress and input from families in setting learning goals for children	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum
5. Use parent questionnaires in appropriate languages on how satisfied they were with teacher-parent communication	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum
6. Aware the culture influence on their own beliefs and practices. Use self-report questionnaires to teachers asking them to identify effective practices, areas of weakness and strength in teaching with children and families from diverse background	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum
7. Use a variety of formal and informal strategies, like conversations and questionnaires, to learn about socioeconomic, linguistic, racial, religious and cultural difference of families from diverse back grounds.	Good	Exceptional	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum
8. Create welcoming learning environment including representation of traditions, history and holidays of program participants in the classroom and in daily activities	Minimum	Exceptional	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum
9. Provide opportunities for children and their families to share their culture by storytelling, puppets, other oral tradition, video, films, music, etc.	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum	Minimum

Field Observation and Debrief Results

Awareness of multicultural teaching

Preservice teachers were aware that diversity exists in the classrooms. This theme emerged first from the internship observations and was discussed during interview question four. The inclusive conversation was evidence of multicultural awareness. For example, one preservice teacher had a conversation about social differences with children, like what are the buildings in the pictures for? The buildings could be a pizza store, grocery store, bus stop, buffalo wings. Some children shared they get food from the pizza store; some shared that their parents work in a store; some shared they have been to a bus stop. The conversation about different buildings provided an opportunity for children to express their daily life experience with peers and teachers.

The awareness of multicultural teaching does not only build inclusive conversation but also reduces prejudice that is caused by lack of knowledge about other cultures (Banks & Banks, 2004). One preservice teacher picked a book that included a diverse family when children asked her to read. She also invited students to talk about their families during reading. While having conversations with students, preservice teachers were intentionally including students with diverse backgrounds. For example, when children were discussing houses and their homes, a preservice teacher said some people live in apartments as well; homes are everywhere in the community.

Build positive relationships with diverse students and their families.

The inclusive conversations can build positive relationships between teachers and diverse families. Some preservice teachers were greeting families and children early in the mornings and having conversations at drop off time. They built connections with families during their internship. From conversations like daily routine, work, fun moments with children, parents appear to be happy with and trust the preservice teacher. One preservice teacher said: "Being in my internship five days a week helps a lot. I get to see them every day and talk to the parent. My previous internship experience was in a much more diverse district also helps a lot..." This preservice teacher was placed in relatively diverse classrooms in current and previous internships. She felt confident and capable to use CRT. Another preservice teacher said: "It took some time for me to know the families...It does help me understand them after that." This preservice teacher stated that she became more confident after she learned more about the families and the teaching team. However, it takes time to build this

relationship since she did not have much experience with diverse family before. Having conversations or background information of families enable preservice teachers to learn and engage with families.

Response students with comfort, respect, and positivity.

Another theme found in this study is to respond to students with comfort, respect, and positivity. These are equity pedagogy practices. A preservice teacher was sitting at the breakfast table with a small group, while talking with students about how their morning was going. The conversation went from breakfast to stories from last night, sibling games, grandma's visits, etc. During these conversations, children were comfortably following instructions of the preservice teacher like "holding bowl with one hand", "using a spoon", "finishing chewing before talking", etc.

One example of the breakfast conversations:

Teacher: "I saw your grandma sent you to school today."

Child: "I didn't catch the bus" (child eating cereal)

Teacher: "Why didn't you catch the bus?"

Child: "We were playing a game, a ball hit me." (child stopped eating)

Teacher: "Were you not feeling good?" (teacher patted child's back)

Child: "Yeah." (child continue eating)

Allow flexibilities and cultural preference in classrooms.

Allowing flexibility and cultural preference can reduce prejudice in the classroom. For example, preservice teachers have conversations with children: "That girl has short hair. Some boys have long hair. Some girls have short hair." However, some preservice teachers were not consistent with the CRT framework. A preservice teacher stated: "diversity doesn't affect our teaching much. We see them all the same." It seems that she believed that treating everyone "equally" was a correct way to implement CRT. An equity pedagogy is not about equality but about meeting each child's individual needs and preferences.

Encourage students to speak and express themselves in small groups.

Practicing equity pedagogy requires student engagement. While doing a group activity, a preservice teacher picked up a red marker and ask a volunteer to count numbers. The teacher said: "I picked red because I know you like it", while she was talking to a boy who needs encouragement to talk in front of a group. The little boy showed excitement and picked up the red marker from teacher and led the number counting. However, a negative example of interacting with children occurred when a preservice teacher solved a conflict between two children. Without investigating what happened, the preservice teacher told one child to say "sorry" to another child. This interaction discouraged children from talking and explaining their thoughts and ideas.

Conclusion

This research was conducted after an in-class CRT workshop with a cohort of early childhood preservice teachers. This cohort was also observed and interviewed during their internship after completing the modified courses. The interview revealed five practical findings: students gained an awareness of multicultural teaching; they built positive relationships with diverse students and their families; they responded to children with comfort, respect, and positivity; they advocated to have children's cultural backgrounds represented in the classroom; they encouraged children to share about their cultural in small groups. The results were used to evaluate the effectiveness of the programmatic changes that were made to improve students' understanding and implementation of culturally responsive teaching practices.

Figure 1

Two Tier Multicultural Teacher Education Model

A paper on theories of multicultural education
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Recommendations

In this study, 27 preservice teachers in early childhood education program were observed and interviewed during their internship period. The internship sites were mixed with predominantly white classrooms and diverse classrooms. All 27 preservice teachers were from the same undergraduate program, and even attended most courses together with the same instructors. However, results show that the awareness, strategies, and decision-makings from these preservice teachers are different. We will explain the differences with three research questions stated before.

First, how do preservice early childhood teachers view classroom diversity? Preservice teachers who actively initiated diversity conversations stated that they view diversity as an essential component in teaching, because of their family background and previous teaching experience in diverse districts. Others explained why they didn't pay attention to the diversity content in teaching so much: 1. they felt that there is little diversity to talk about while teaching in a majority white classroom; 2. they didn't understand the individual needs of minority students; 3. they had no personal connections to the diverse population. It appears that previous experiences have a significant impact on preservice teachers' focus on CRT.

Second, what are the strategies preservice early childhood teacher used to build teacher-family relationship? The connections between teacher and family start with morning greetings every day. Many preservice teachers stated that the frequency of their internship days makes a difference. It is easier for preservice teachers who attend internship five days a week to build teacher-family relationships. In addition to morning greetings, preservice teachers found other ways to get to know and improve their relationship with families. For example, they learned more about cultural diversity from reviewing family and child profiles; communicating with mentor teachers; and initiating conversations about families with students.

The last question is how do preservice teacher make classroom decisions and facilitate student participations with multicultural topics? There are three major findings on this question: Respond to students with respect, and positivity. Be flexible and allow children to share their cultural background in the classroom; Encourage students to speak and express themselves in small groups. All three practices support children from diverse backgrounds by creating a safe, encouraging, and respectful environment.

The results of that study revealed a need to improve how we integrate CRT content and the activities in the program to help students understand CRT and apply it in their clinical experiences. Preservice teachers in this study showed different levels of CRT competence. For example, some preservice teachers engaged children with multicultural materials, activities, and conversations about their families. Meanwhile, some preservice teachers struggled with CRT strategies and classroom management. This study showed that the CRT workshop had a positive effect on some preservice teachers.

This study proposed to explore how early childhood teacher preparation CRT. Systematic changes and interventions need to happen, so that teachers can not only believe, but live out the values of equality and diversity. Here are some suggestions for implementing the CRT framework in teacher education programs:

1. Apply a multicultural model in the program courses that support students to reflect on their racial identity and biases.
2. Incorporate information about different cultural groups in all methods courses to increase students' cultural knowledge so they can develop culturally inclusive lesson plans.
3. Require at least one clinical experience in a diverse classrooms or virtual classroom to interact with students from different cultural backgrounds.

4. Assign a project in a culminating course that requires students to develop a plan for ensuring racial equity in all aspects of their teaching.

Limitations

The internship placement sites are at different levels of diversity, which may cause variance in the study results. Although they were all asked to reflect on CRT practices, the more diverse settings may provide more opportunities for preservice teacher to implement CRT practices.

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